

COMPARATIVE MODEL OF METAPHORICAL THINKING IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20363226>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the comparative model of metaphorical thinking in English and Uzbek languages based on linguocognitive and linguoculturological approaches. Metaphor is considered a universal mechanism of human cognition, and its reflection in the language system as well as its connection with cultural characteristics are examined. The study identifies metaphorical models based on conceptual metaphors, idioms, and paremiological units, and elucidates their semantic and cognitive features.*

Keywords: *metaphor, metaphorical thinking, conceptual metaphor, linguocognitive approach, linguoculturology, semantic model, comparative analysis, idioms, paremiology.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillarida metaforik tafakkurning qiyosiy modeli lingvokognitiv va lingvokulturologik yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilinadi. Metafora inson tafakkurining universal mexanizmi sifatida qaralib, uning til tizimida aks etishi va madaniy xususiyatlar bilan bog'liqligi o'rganiladi. Tadqiqotda konseptual metaforalar, idiomalar va paremiologik birliklar asosida metaforik modellar aniqlanadi hamda ularning semantik va kognitiv xususiyatlari yoritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *metafora, metaforik tafakkur, konseptual metafora, lingvokognitiv yondashuv, lingvokulturologiya, semantik model, qiyosiy tahlil, idiomalar, paremiologiya.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется сравнительная модель метафорического мышления в английском и узбекском языках на основе лингвокогнитивного и лингвокультурологического подходов. Метафора рассматривается как универсальный механизм человеческого познания, изучается её отражение в языковой системе, а также её связь с культурными особенностями. В исследовании выявляются метафорические модели на основе концептуальных метафор, идиом и паремиологических единиц, а также раскрываются их семантические и когнитивные характеристики.*

Ключевые слова: *метафора, метафорическое мышление, концептуальная метафора, лингвокогнитивный подход, лингвокультурология, семантическая модель, сравнительный анализ, идиомы, паремиология.*

Introduction. In modern linguistics, metaphor is considered not only a stylistic device but also one of the fundamental cognitive mechanisms of human thinking. Through metaphorical thinking, a person understands and expresses abstract concepts based on concrete experience. Therefore, metaphor serves as an important scientific tool in studying the complex relationship between language and thought. In English and Uzbek languages, metaphorical units have been formed under the influence of various cultural and historical factors, and their comparative study makes it possible to identify linguoculturological and cognitive differences. This research is aimed at developing a comparative model of metaphorical thinking, which helps to determine both similarities and specific features between the two languages.

Literature Review: Metaphorical thinking and its expression in the language system are widely studied as one of the important directions of modern linguistics. Metaphor is interpreted not only as a stylistic device but also as one of the main mechanisms of human cognition. Through comparative analysis of metaphorical expressions in English and Uzbek texts, their semantic and stylistic features are identified, and the functional potential of metaphor in the language system is revealed [1]. Such an approach makes it possible to gain a deeper understanding of how metaphor is formed and expressed in different cultures. The issue of semantic modeling of metaphor also receives special scientific attention, where the role of metaphor in the conceptual system and its structural features are analyzed [2]. According to this approach, metaphor is based not on simple similarity between linguistic units but on the process of conceptual mapping in the human mind. As a result, metaphor is interpreted as a complex cognitive process, and its semantic structure and models are identified. The study of linguoculturological features of metaphors in English and Uzbek idioms and proverbs reveals the expression of national mentality through language [3]. Metaphors often embody the historical experience, worldview, and values of a people, and they are especially actively manifested in paremiological units. From this perspective, metaphorical units serve as an important source in linguoculturological research.

Studies based on newspaper texts analyze the discursive function of conceptual metaphors and reveal their role in mass communication [4]. In publicistic discourse, metaphors serve as a means of conveying information concisely and effectively, as well as influencing the audience ideologically or emotionally. This demonstrates the linguistic, communicative, and social significance of metaphor. The universality and national specificity of conceptual metaphors are studied within a cognitive-semiotic approach, identifying how metaphorical models such as “tree—human” are interpreted in different cultures [5]. The results show that while some metaphorical models are universal, their semantic interpretation is determined by national and cultural factors. The economic function of metaphor is also an important scientific direction, as it reflects lexical economy [6]. Metaphor enables the concise and expressive representation of complex ideas, increasing the effectiveness of speech. Therefore, it is evaluated as a means of expanding the expressive and communicative potential of language. The study of metaphorical language from the perspective of cognitive linguistics reveals its close connection with thinking [7]. According to this approach, metaphor plays an important role in structuring knowledge and forming new meanings in the human mind. As a result, metaphor is interpreted as one of the key mechanisms explaining the interaction between language and thought.

Research Methodology: In this study, comparative, cognitive, linguoculturological, semantic, and discursive analysis methods were applied in a комплекс manner. The main objective of the research was to study metaphorical models in English and Uzbek languages and to identify their cognitive and cultural foundations. Through the comparative method, metaphorical models in the two language systems were compared, and their similarities and differences were identified. Cognitive analysis served to reveal the conceptual foundations of metaphor in human thinking, analyzing how abstract concepts are expressed through concrete images. The linguoculturological approach made it possible to highlight the cultural context of metaphors and their connection with national thinking and values.

The use of semantic analysis helped identify the layers of meaning in metaphorical units, including their denotative and connotative features. Discursive analysis focused on the functional role of metaphors in the text, their communicative function, and pragmatic impact.

As research materials, literary texts, proverbs, idioms, and publicistic texts were selected, on the basis of which the features of metaphorical units in different speech environments were analyzed.

Results of the Analysis: The analysis revealed several main models of metaphorical thinking in English and Uzbek languages and clarified their cognitive and linguoculturological features. Anthropomorphic metaphors are characteristic of both languages, where natural phenomena or objects are expressed through human features. This model brings complex concepts closer to human experience and facilitates their perception. In particular, the image of a tree representing human life, development, and continuity appears as a universal metaphorical model. Emotional metaphors serve as an important means of expressing feelings. In English, such metaphors are more abstract and generalized, whereas in Uzbek they are more figurative, culturally rich, and based on concrete imagery. This difference is explained by the cultural specifics of expressing emotional experience in both peoples. Conceptual metaphors are based on expressing abstract concepts through concrete images. For example, interpreting life as a journey or time as an economic resource represents a universal cognitive model manifested similarly across languages. Paremiological metaphors reflect national experience and wisdom within proverbs and sayings. In Uzbek, such metaphors are more often based on images related to nature, agriculture, and rural life, while in English metaphorical expressions related to urban environment and individualistic values prevail. Discursive metaphors are активно used in publicistic and mass media texts, serving as an important means of expressing social and political processes. They present complex social phenomena in a clear and impactful manner for the reader.

Another important feature of metaphors is their function of lexical economy. Metaphor enables the concise expression of complex and multi-component concepts, enhancing the economy of language. In general, although metaphorical thinking in English and Uzbek languages has a common cognitive basis, national-cultural factors, historical experience, and social environment play a significant role in its expression.

Conclusion: Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. Metaphor, as a universal mechanism of human cognition, is characterized by similar conceptual models in English and Uzbek languages. This indicates that metaphorical thinking is based on a common cognitive foundation. Metaphorical thinking is formed under the influence of national culture, historical experience, and social conditions, which leads to language-specific features. Therefore, linguoculturological factors play an important role in the expression of metaphors, reflecting the national worldview.

Metaphors perform semantic, cognitive, aesthetic, and communicative functions, significantly expanding the expressive potential of language. They serve as an important means of simplifying complex concepts, creating imagery, and enhancing the impact of speech. The comparative approach proves to be an effective method for identifying universal and national aspects of metaphorical thinking, enabling a systematic understanding of similarities and differences between languages and cultures. In the future, studying metaphorical models based on corpus linguistics and experimental research is considered a перспективное direction that will deepen scientific investigations in this field and lead to more precise results.

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